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Providing secure mechanisms to protect personal data in a mobility platform

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Abstract

Security and privacy preserving methods need to be developed to facilitate cloud usage even for organisations dealing with sensitive information and maintaining security critical services. A reasonable way to achieve the required security properties for outsourced data storage and processing thereby is by adopting suitable cryptographic mechanisms. Results of two European funded projects are combined to achieve a platform for inclusive mobility enhanced by cryptographic services which ensure protection of actual sensitive data of mobility impaired users.

Keywords:

privacy, cryptography, mobility, impaired users

Introduction

The use of cloud computing as a service has become a successful tool for quite many years now. A platform designed to provide mobility services can turn into a marketable product/service if we consider planning cloud computing, mobile app development, real-time management for Public Authorities, services integration, and privacy preservation tools. Moreover, Privacy by design is paramount and must be taken as a fundamental part in the approach when implementing this kind of systems. The overall framework must consider privacy and trust from the very beginning in the design of systems and processes, including social and human aspects in the engineering process, following the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [1] principles.

Motivation

In the field of transport and mobility, technologies must ensure the integrity, confidentiality and secure handling of data, including personal and financial details, and show that citizens' rights are fully protected. With advancing technology and diversified data sources more data is in principle available. An important issue is the definition of the roles of the public and private sector especially on

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co-operation on data access and exchange.

The European Commission promotes in its strategy "Digital Agenda for Europe / Europe 2020" the rapid adoption of cloud computing in all sectors of the economy to boost productivity. Furthermore, EC concludes that "cloud computing has the potential to slash users' IT expenditure and to enable many new services to be developed. Using the cloud, even the smallest firms can reach out to ever larger markets while governments can make their services more attractive and efficient even while reining in spending." [2]. However, besides these advantages of cloud computing, many new problems arise which are not yet sufficiently solved, especially with respect to information security and privacy. Novel security and privacy preserving methods need to be developed to facilitate cloud usage even for organisations dealing with sensitive information and maintaining security critical services. The only reasonable way to achieve the required security properties for outsourced data storage and processing thereby is by adopting suitable cryptographic mechanisms.

PRISMACLOUD project [3] yields a portfolio of novel security enabled cloud services, guaranteeing the required security for sensitive data in the cloud. Techniques for outsourcing computation with verifiable correctness and authenticity-preservation allow to securely delegate computations to cloud providers. A distributed multi-cloud data storage architecture shares data among several cloud providers and improves security and availability.

Claims about the secure connection and configuration of the virtualized cloud infrastructures and properties of cloud topologies are verifiable by means of cryptographic techniques. User privacy issues are addressed by data minimization and anonymization technologies due to the application of privacy-preserving cryptographic techniques. Therefore, there is a need for innovative solutions based on efficient cryptographic techniques for cloud computing. These techniques improve the security of data at rest, data in move, and data in use as well as the privacy of cloud users.

For many services in the cloud, it is important that users are given means to prove that they are authorised to perform or delegate a certain task. However, it is not always necessary that users reveal their full identity to the cloud, but only prove by some means that they are authorised, e.g., possess certain rights. Thereby, the main obstacle is that a cloud provider must still be cryptographically reassured that the user is authorised.

The SIMON system

The SIMON system has been developed, implemented and deployed in the context of the SIMON Project [4]. It focuses on the reduction of fraud in the pre-ICT implementation of the European Disabled Badge for public parking areas and the use of specific navigation solutions for elderly and people with disabilities.

The SIMON system [5], [6] allows the implementation and deployment of new solutions based on an inclusive mobility approach which relays on concepts such as accessibility, design-for-all and privacy of data, that has to result in an innovative system which has to provide:

1. A mobile application and web platform as an open communication channel with citizens, including

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specific navigation features supporting the mobility of disabled people.

2. The capability for authorities to promote inclusion policies –e.g. coordinated advantageous transport tariffs - whilst fighting against fraud –e.g. univocal identification of user and disabled parking badge.
3. Specific IT solutions for specific targeted end-users. Mobile applications for navigation, e-id, etc; smart cards for e-ticketing and e-id; or combination of both when required. Always with a focus on usability and user-friendliness.
4. New mobility schemas supporting the access of elderly and disabled people to the same opportunities as the rest of citizens.

SIMON Mobile is an application for navigation, orientation and parking designed for persons with reduced mobility. The application is currently available in the Android and iOS versions and it can be downloaded freely from the Google Play and Apple Stores. SIMON Mobile integrates with a new concept of the EU parking card for the disabled that has been tested in a large-scale pilot running at several European cities. The goal of this ICT-enhanced badge is to reduce the fraudulent use of disabled parking bays to ensure that they are available to the persons that really need them. Combined with a SIMON disabled badge, disabled citizens can use Simon Mobile to validate for parking and to view the usage history of their badge.

The EU standardised model of parking card for the disabled [7] (commonly known as Blue Badge) allows a disabled person who is entitled to use certain parking facilities in his EU country of residence to move more easily in the territory of another EU country and avail themselves of all the parking facilities granted to the card-holders in that EU country. Nevertheless, the misuse of the European parking card for disabled people has become a reality and a headache for public authorities in charge of managing the permissions and the use of the public space for parking purposes. Furthermore, accessibility issues concern persons with disabilities and older population, and technology is required to promote successful actions that enable them to live more equally alongside those people without disabilities. To reduce fraud, SIMON enhances the European parking card for disabled people with contactless technologies and integrates mobile solutions to support user unique identification in existing park meters whilst preserving privacy. Therefore, one of the main outcomes of the SIMON project was the specification of this ICT-enhanced parking card for mobility impaired users. It must include a set of security tokens to be used in the authentication of users. SIMON information model must allow interoperability of the proposed solution in order that a same model of the parking card can be used and security tokens are recognized as a non-isolated solution.

The elements that make the paper card become a smart parking card are the following:

1. A **user identity (USER ID)** associated to each user, to be printed in the card.
2. **QR code images (QR Code)** to be glued or printed in the card. It is recommended to have one in the front and a copy of it in the back.
3. **NFC tag** to be incorporated in a sticker or by any other mechanism (one per badge). The NFC Code, which is provided by the manufacturer of the NFC tag, shall be not-modifiable.

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Figure 1 – ICT-enhanced SIMON parking card and SIMON Mobile app for validation

Next-generation secure cloud services

PRISMACLOUD brings novel cryptographic concepts and methods to practical application by improving the security and privacy of services from the early stages and making them usable for providers and users. For data in move and in use PRISMACLOUD develops techniques that preserve data authenticity throughout all processes. In particular these techniques guarantee that the computations yield correct results and that the data do not lose their authenticity and confidentiality. These novel cryptographic tools, mechanisms, and techniques are ready to be used in a cloud environment, in order to:

- protect the security of data over its lifecycle,
- protect the privacy of the users,
- securely compose services,
- base the security and privacy on 'by design' principles, and
- to provide efficient implementations both at software and hardware level.

Anonymous credential systems have proved to be an important concept for privacy-preserving applications as they allow users to authenticate in an anonymous way without revealing any more information than necessary to be authenticated at a service. The underlying building blocks of state-of-the-art anonymous credential systems moreover can be used in the design of various related concepts such as group signatures, privacy protecting multi-coupon systems, anonymous subscriptions, e-cash systems and many more. PRISMACLOUD innovates with a focus on their application in cloud computing services.

To demonstrate the capabilities of methods and tools developed within PRISMACLOUD, they are evaluated and validated in dedicated application scenarios. Moreover, selected components and tools are integrated in different combinations to gain in security for representative tasks within a certain domain. The tools have been integrated in cloud test-beds at multiple sites identical to real-life service scenarios and their performance has been validated under realistic assumptions. This approach demonstrates to service providers how they can migrate parts of their systems to cloud environments

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with increased security.

Two main services of those developed in PRISMACLOUD are used to provide secure mechanisms in the SIMON system:

Privacy Enhancing IDM

The service offers client applications the possibility to manage their pool of users in a privacy-preserving manner. Operations needing authorization and susceptible of revealing sensible information about the users can be secured by setting a group-based permission system where individuals provide an anonymous proof of their inclusion in a group (which may be linked to a certain set of permissions), which is used by the application to authorize the action.

Encryption Proxy

This service encrypts sensitive information identified within communication traffic in a format and/or order preserving way. In this sense, the communication messages pass through this service and they are encrypted in two ways:

- (a) Format Preserving Encryption (FPE): encrypted version of the items follows the same format as the original items, thus allowing the server and databases to work with the encrypted version of the data the same way they would do with the plain-text data.
- (b) Order Preserving Encryption (OPE): in addition to the format, this encryption mechanism ensures that the encrypted version of the items follows the same order the plain-text data would follow. This particularity becomes especially useful for data among which range queries are performed, as, for instance, times-tamps.

SIMON in the cloud

The implementation of the ICT parking card and the SIMON management system requires extensive integration of multiple databases with dedicated private and sensitive information, ideally to be hosted and shared (by different municipalities and other stakeholders) in the cloud. Thus, a challenge is the instantiation of mechanisms for data privacy preservation, including cryptographic means. On the one hand, data stored in large distributed databases should be encrypted by advanced techniques but still possible to validate. In this sense, encryption and tokenization schemes provide this functionality for data bases and ease data sharing. On the other hand, personalized data is stored and logged in the system, which invades peoples' private sphere. Care must be taken to protect user privacy while still extract data for usage analysis and service optimization. The solution consists of implementing efficient big data anonymization techniques to improve user privacy.

SIMON system cloudification ensures that data stored by third parties is secured with cryptographic means. Besides, SIMON operation is focused on privacy issues, so the users of the system cannot be tracked by any means.

SIMON backoffice system is running in private instances and is in a private datacenter, which is located at ETRA I+D facilities. The service can be now secured in two steps:

The first one is the cloudification of SIMON, that is, to move the current application to the cloud. This

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implies to encrypt sensitive data, through the Encryption Proxy (EPaaS) service which will be used to encrypt sensitive fields on the fly.

The functionality of SIMON remains the same, but it is located at the cloud. In this sense, we add a security layer by encryption with minimum modifications of the system, as it is shown in Figure 2:

Figure 2: Diagram of the cloudification of SIMON

Since it is located in the cloud, new security requirements around the managed data arise. The focus is put in the reduction of fraud, since it is more sensitive to privacy and security issues.

The flow of interactions among components is exposed in Figure 3:

Figure 3: Components interactions in SIMON cloudification

- Messages going to and coming from the smartphones (citizens and controllers) will pass through Trusted Point. These messages have clear text.
- Then, sensitive information is encrypted on the fly, by calling the FPE/OPE Service.
- A direct communication channel to the cloud will still exist for exploitation operations where no personal information of the users is required (retrieving statistics of the system, for instance).

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The second step is the anonymization of SIMON. The user is not identified by the system any more and can maintain his/her privacy, so the identifier of the user is replaced by a proof of belonging to a group. This change includes the use of Privacy Enhancing Identifier Management (PIDM) service. PIDM service manages a set of attribute credentials instead of using private data. Current SIMON services need to be modified in order to support the cryptographic features needed to avoid the processing of actual users' identification when validating and controlling parking lot uses. PIDM service will present a redacted version of the credentials that can be verified. This verification will ensure the user is allowed to access the system.

In this use case components communicate among them in the way depicted in Figure 4:

Figure 4: Components interaction in SIMON anonymization

The communication among elements in this system is as follows:

- The user asks for permission to park at area N application by sending its location and a proof of his/her credentials.
- SIMON application asks for the proof validation to the PIDMaaS.
- SIMON application gives the operation identification to the user. This identification is a unique identifier.

A new prototype of the SIMON Mobile app has been built, which integrates the PRISMACLOUD PIDMaaS. The validation of the parking badge is performed in the same way but now the system does not know about personal data of users any more.

When the holder of the disable badge asks for permission the PIDM transforms the identifier (SIMON ID) into the proof of permission. Parking controllers only check the proof, and authorities only receive anonymized statistics. As shown in Figure 5, visualization tools of the public authority show anonymized data: a Location ID (not user ID), a Validation timestamp and if requested, groups of users which can be configured in the system.

Figure 5: Visualization tools and anonymized data

Conclusions

Currently, applications in the mobility domain involve handling lots of data and information coming from users, which most of times require the adoption of measures to ensure privacy protection and correct management of sensitive data. The specific case of data related to mobility impaired users is a good example, but actually any app in the market related to transport is facing the same issues, even more in the new business models adoption based on Mobility as a Service and the Internet of Things. The Privacy Enhancing IDM service (PIDMaaS) can be used to set up a privacy-aware permission system. Individuals are given cryptographic tokens accordingly to their set of permissions. They can further use those tokens to generate proofs of their permission to access to some resources in a group without revealing their identity. On the other hand, the encryption proxy service can be employed by any organization willing to move an existing distributed application server that handles sensitive data (e.g., personal data) to the cloud. This service provides a proxy that will capture all traffic between the clients and the cloudified server, and will perform encryption and decryption of sensitive fields on the fly.

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